

Stability Indicating Method Development and Validation of Polmacoxib in Bulk and Capsule Dosage Form by Rp-Hplc Method

Indhumathi K.^{1*}, Murugan S.², Vetrichelvan T.³

¹M. Pharm Student, ²Associate Professor, ³HOD cum Dean Research, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Adhiparasakthi College of Pharmacy, Melmaruvathur-603319, Tamil Nadu, Affiliated to The Tamil Nadu Dr. M. G. R. Medical University, Chennai-600 032, India

ABSTRACT

A Simple, rapid, economical, precise and accurate Stability indicating RP- HPLC method for the estimation of Polmacoxib has been developed. A reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method was developed for the estimation of Polmacoxib has been developed. The separation was achieved Column Shimadzu C18 (4.6 x 250 mm, 5µm), isocratic program Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (40:40:20 % v/v/v) as a mobile phase, at the flow rate of 1 ml/min. Detection was carried out at 316 nm and the retention time of Polmacoxib was found to be 3.658 min. The method has been validated for linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, ruggedness. Linearity observed for Polmacoxib 12-60 µg/ml. Developed method was found to be accurate, precise and rapid and time consuming for estimation of Polmacoxib and the drug was subjected to stress condition of acidic, basic, oxidation, reduction, UV light degradation, under same chromatographic condition. The stress samples were assayed on RP-HPLC system.

Keywords: Polmacoxib, RP- HPLC Method, Stability indicating method, method development and Validation.

INTRODUCTION

Polmacoxib is a selective cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) inhibitor, belonging to the class of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). Its chemical structure is characterized by a benzothiazole ring system, which is essential for its COX-2 selectivity. The molecule features a sulphonamide group and an aromatic ring, contributing to its pharmacological activity. Polmacoxib exhibits its primary action by selectively inhibiting COX-2, an enzyme involved in the synthesis of prostaglandins that mediate inflammation and pain. By targeting COX-2 over COX-1, Polmacoxib reduces inflammation, pain, and fever with a lower risk of gastrointestinal side effects compared to non-selective NSAIDs that inhibit both COX-1 and COX-2. This selective inhibition contributes to its efficacy in managing inflammatory conditions while minimizing adverse effects on the gastric mucosa. Polmacoxib is used primarily in the treatment of osteoarthritis and other chronic inflammatory conditions (10).

Osteoarthritis is described as a chronic and painful joint disease, in which the patient experiences acute joint pain, inflammation, bone remodelling and even disability which are caused due to breakage of cartilage present between the bone joints. Osteoarthritis cases has been growing more immensely in recent years due to increase in certain factors like obesity, unhealthy lifestyle, inactivity, poor posture, etc. There are various first line medications for treatment of arthritis and inflammation which involves paracetamol, and especially for Osteoarthritis and Rheumatoid arthritis treatment there are various Cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors, also known as COXIBs, which help in reduction of inflammation and pain like- Valdecoxib, Rofecoxib, Celecoxib, Polmacoxib. But most of the COXIBs like Valdecoxib, Rofecoxib, etc. has been removed from the market due to the increasing side effects in patients including cardiovascular toxicity and gastrointestinal toxicity. Polmacoxib is one of the recently introduced COX-II inhibitors which is a Non-

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Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drug (NSAID) class of drug (2).

There is no method developed in High-performance liquid chromatography by using this mobile phase. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) stands as a powerful analytical tool in modern chemistry. It excels at identifying, measuring, and separating components within liquid-dissolved samples. Widely employed in pharmacological product analysis, HPLC is prized for its precision in both quantitative and qualitative assessments, contributing significantly to advancements in analytical chemistry. In high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), a sample solution (stationary phase) is injected into a porous column. A liquid (mobile phase) is then pumped through the column at high pressure. Components in the sample exhibit different migration rates through the column due to partitioning between stationary and mobile phases. This leads to elution at distinct times, allowing separation. HPLC's precision arises from nuanced component behaviours during partitioning, offering a robust method for analysing diverse samples in fields like pharmaceuticals and analytical chemistry (3).

Figure 1. Structure of Celecoxib

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Instrumentation:

The instrument used in the present study was Shimadzu Lc-2030 Plus (Auto), Shimadzu Lc-20AD (Manual), Shimadzu C₁₈ 4.6×250 mm, 5 μm. All weighing was done on electronic balance (Model Shimadzu AUX - 220).

Reagents and Chemicals:

All chemical and reagent of HPLC graded were purchased from Qualigens India Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India. The pharmaceutical dosage form used in this

study was Polixar capsule contains equivalent to 2 mg of Polmacoxib per capsule. Acetonitrile, methanol, HPLC water, sulphuric acid, Hydrogen peroxide, sodium bisulfite, potassium hydroxide was used.

Preparation of standard and sample solution

Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial contains various mobile phase which are considered of Acetonitrile, Methanol and Water in different proportions and different volumes at different flow rate were tried. On the basis of various trial, the Mobile phase was used Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (40:40:20 % v/v/v) at 1 ml/min flow rate, proved to be better than the other mixture in terms of peak shape, theoretical plate and a symmetry.

Diluent

Methanol was used as a diluent.

Mobile phase

Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (40:40:20, % v/v/v) is programmed as RP HPLC method.

Preparation of mobile phase

Added 400 ml of acetonitrile, 400 ml of methanol and added 200 ml of water. Mixed well, sonicated for 10 minutes and degassed.

Preparation of standard stock solution

Accurately weighed quantity of 20 mg of Polmacoxib API was transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark. From this standard stock solution, 1.5 ml was withdrawn and diluted to 10 ml using methanol to get working concentration of 120 μg/ml.

Preparation of working standard solution

From above standard stock solution of Polmacoxib, 2ml of solution was taken into 10 ml volumetric flask and was made to the mark with the methanol to get 24 μg/ml of Polmacoxib.

Preparation of sample stock solution

The average weight of 20 capsules was determined. Sample stock solution was prepared by dissolving

capsule powder equivalent to 2 mg of Polmacoxib was transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask. Then 15 ml methanol was added and sonicated for 15 mins to ensure complete solubilization of drug. After sonication, volume was made up to the mark with methanol. Filter the stock solution with Whatman filter paper. Then, 3 ml was withdrawn and diluted to 10 ml using methanol to get concentration of 24 µg/ml of a sample solution.

VALIDATION (4)

The proposed methods were validated as per ICH guidelines.

Linearity

Different aliquots of 1.0 - 5.0 ml of standard stock solution was transferred into series of 10 ml volumetric flasks, separately and the volume was made up to the mark with methanol to get concentrations 12, 24, 36, 48 and 60 µg/ml, respectively.

Accuracy

To the preanalysed sample solution, a known amount of standard stock solution was added at different levels i.e. 50, 100 and 150%. The solutions were reanalyzed by proposed method.

Precision

The reproducibility of this method was determined by analysing capsules at different time intervals on same day in triplicates (Intra-day assay precision) and on three different days (Inter-day assay precision).

Robustness

The Robustness was evaluated by wavelength, flow rate and mobile phase ratio. During the studies of Robustness there was not much changes in retention time, and symmetry of peak. The effect of changes was found to be with in the acceptance criteria. The % RSD should be less than 2%.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness of the proposed method is determined by analysed the aliquots from homogeneous slot by two analyst and two instrument using different operational and environmental conditions.

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation

They were measured using standard deviation of Y-intercept and slope of calibration curve as per ICH guideline. The LOD and LOQ were calculated using following formula

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / s$$

Where,

σ = the standard deviation of response

s = the slope of the calibration curve

FORCED DEGRADATION

Acid degradation

Acid decomposition studies were performed by transferring 2 ml of standard stock solution in to 10 ml of volumetric flask. 2 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ solutions was added and mixed well and kept for 24 hrs at 60°C. After time period 2 ml of 0.1 N KOH Added to neutralize the solution and make up the volume with diluent (5,7).

Base degradation

Base decomposition studies were performed by transferring 2 ml of standard stock solution in to 10 ml of volumetric flask. 2 ml of 0.1 N KOH solutions was added and mixed well and kept for 24 hrs at 60°C. After time period 2 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ Added to neutralize the solution and make up the volume with diluent (5,7).

Oxidation degradation

Oxidation decomposition studies were performed by transferring 2 ml of standard stock solution in to 10 ml of volumetric flask. 2 ml of 1 % H₂O₂ solutions was added and mixed well and kept for 24 hrs at 60°C. After time period make up the volume with diluent (5).

Reduction degradation

Reduction decomposition studies were performed by transferring 2 ml of standard stock solution in to 10 ml of volumetric flask. 2 ml of 10 % sodium bisulfite solutions was added and mixed well and put for 24 hrs

at 60°C. After time period make up the volume with diluent (6).

UV light degradation

UV light degradation studies were performed by transferred accurately weighed 20 mg of Polmacoxib raw material (previously kept in UV light for 24 h) into 25 ml volumetric flask made up the volume with diluent. Dilute 1.5 ml of stock solution in to 10 ml of volumetric flask and made up the volume with diluent. Dilute 2 ml from the above solution into the 10 ml volumetric flask and made up the volume with diluent. Inject the solution into the HPLC system (8).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION

The HPLC procedure was optimized with a view to develop a suitable LC method for the determination of Polmacoxib in capsule dosage form. Initially difference ratios of mobile phase were used and finalized the Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (40:40:20 % v/v/v) as a mobile phase. This is shown in table 1. In this ratio of 40:40:20 % (v/v/v) gave acceptable retention time (3.658 minutes) with flow rate of 1.0 ml/min as shown in figure 3 and also performed methanol as a blank shown in figure 2.

Fig: 2 Optimization blank peak with mobile phase Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (40:40:20 %v/v/v)

Fig: 3 Optimization peak with mobile phase Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (40:40:20 % v/v/v)

Table 1: Mobile phase selection

S.no	Mobile phase composition	Interference
1	Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (30:30:40 % v/v/v)	Peak elutes very late
2	Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (15:25:60 % v/v/v)	Peak did not elute
3	Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (40:40:20 % v/v/v)	Proper peak shape, peaks Baseline noise reduced, Tailing factor less than 2.

METHOD VALIDATION

The described method has been validated which include parameters like system suitability, linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, ruggedness, LOD (limit of detection) and LOQ (limit of quantification).

System suitability

System suitability and chromatographic parameters were validated such as tailing factor and theoretical plates was calculated. The results are given in table 2.

Table 2: system suitability parameters

S.no	Parameter	Value
1	Retention time	3.658
2	Peak area	1075643
3	Tailing factor	1.080
4	Theoretical plate	4739.10

Linearity

Linearity of this method was evaluated by linear regression analysis and calculated by least square

method and studied by preparing standard solutions of Polmacoxib at different concentrations, in the range of 12-60 µg/ml with correlation coefficient (r²) 0.9998. Results are given in table 3.

Fig: 4 linearity graph of Polmacoxib

Table 3: linearity study of Polmacoxib

S.no	Concentration (µg/ml)	Peak area
1	12	564258
2	24	1075643
3	36	1638267
4	48	2185511
5	60	2720512

PRESICION

Precision was evaluated at the repeatability and intermediate precision levels. For repeatability analysis, six independent portions of a capsule dosage form were processed through the full analytical method and results was evaluated obtained by % RSD values of 0.2072 as shown in table 4.

Table 4: precision of Polmacoxib

Sample no	Label claim (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Purity	% Average	SD*	% RSD*
1	2	2.006	100.32	100.26	0.2077	0.2072
2		2.001	100.05			
3		2.002	100.12			
4		2.006	100.30			
5		2.013	100.63			
6		2.003	100.16			

SD* Standard deviation

RSD* Relative standard deviation

ACCURACY

Accuracy of the proposed method was determined by performing the recovery experiment. The recovery experiment was studied by adding known amount of standard Polmacoxib to the pharmaceutical product

and calculating the recovered standard amount. At 50%, 100% and 150% standard addition level mean recovery of were found to be 100.26%, 100.79% and 99.59 % respectively. The results of recovery experiment are given in table 5.

Table 5: Accuracy of Polmacoxib

Sample	% Concentration	Sample amount (µg/ml)	Amount spiked (µg/ml)	Estimated amount (µg/ml)	Recovered amount (µg/ml)	Average % Recovery	SD	%RSD
POLM	50	24	12	36.03	12.03	100.25	0.0557	0.0555
	100	24	24	48.19	24.19	100.79	0.7434	0.7376
	150	24	36	60.21	36.21	100.58	0.0954	0.0948

ROBUSTNESS

Robustness study was conducted by deliberate changes in mobile phase composition and flow rate,

wavelength, revealed that there was no significant variation in % assay as shown in table 6.

Table 6: Robustness of Polmacoxib

PARAMETER	Amount found (mg/cap)	% ASSAY	SD	% RSD
Flow rate				
0.9 ml/min	1.9960	99.80	0.4677	0.4686
1.0 ml/min	2.0080	100.40	0.1353	0.1347
1.1 ml/min	1.9938	99.69	0.5921	0.594
Mobile phase composition				
Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (40:40:20 % v/v/v)	1.9946	99.73	0.3102	0.3111
Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (39:41:20 % v/v/v)	2.0132	100.66	0.3842	0.3817
Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (42:39:19 % v/v/v)	1.9998	99.99	0.4729	0.4729
315 nm	2.0214	101.07	0.8050	0.7965
316 nm	2.0088	100.44	0.1767	0.1759
317 nm	2.0084	100.42	0.5859	0.5834

RUGGEDNESS

The Ruggedness is calculated and the method showed Ruggedness with the different instrument and different analyst. The data is shown in Table - 7

Table 7: Ruggedness of Polmacoxib

Sample	Concentration	Types of ruggedness*	Average % recovery*	SD	% RSD
POLM	24	Analyst 1	100.41	0.4860	0.4840
		Analyst 2	100.36	0.1389	0.1384
		Instrument 1	100.22	0.2570	0.2564
		Instrument 2	100.33	0.2122	0.2115

Mean of 3 observations (n=3)

POLM* Polmacoxib

OPTICAL CHARACTERIZATION

The LOD and LOQ are calculated by using average value of slope and standard deviation of response

(Intercept). The optical characteristics of the drug at their selected wavelength are shown in Table - 8

Table 8: LOD and LOQ of Polmacoxib

Parameter	Polmacoxib
Regression equation (y= mx+ c)	Y=45307x+10125
Slope (m)	45307
Intercept (c)	4821.6
Correlation coefficient (r ²)	0.9999
SE of intercept	0.19508
S. D	0.47785
LOD (µg/ml)	3.4898
LOQ (µg/ml)	0.000105

FORCED DEGRADATION

Results are tabulated in table 9.

Table 9: Forced degradation of Polmacoxib

Stress condition	Time(h)	% degradation
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	24	Not degraded
0.1M KOH	24	Not degraded
Oxidation	24	Not degraded
Reduction	24	Not degraded
UV light degradation	24	Not degraded

When stress conditions were applied to Polmacoxib results showed there was no degradation occurs in acid, base, oxidative, reduction and UV light degradation.

CONCLUSION

Polmacoxib works by selectively inhibiting the cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzyme, which plays a role in inflammation and pain. Unlike traditional NSAIDs that inhibit both COX-1 and COX-2, selective COX-2 inhibitors are designed to reduce inflammation with a lower risk of gastrointestinal side effects. In RP-HPLC method, was successfully developed for the quantitative estimation of Polmacoxib using a column Shimadzu C₁₈ (4.6×250 mm, 5 μm) with a mobile phase consisting of acetonitrile: methanol: water (40:40:20, % v/v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The detection was carried out at 316 nm and the injection volume was 20 μl. under the optimized chromatographic conditions, the analyte was well resolved with a retention time of 3.658 minutes and no interfering peaks were observed, indicating specificity of the method. System suitability parameters such as theoretical plates (>2000), and % RSD of peak area (<2%) were within acceptable limits, demonstrating the adequacy of the system for analysis. The proposed method was simple, time consuming, accurate, and precise. Therefore, proposed method can be used for routine analysis of Polmacoxib. Forced degradation study of Polmacoxib was performed by RP-HPLC method which includes Acid, Base, Oxidation, Reduction UV light degradation. There is no degradation found in forced degradation study.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All the authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICT OF INTRESTS

Declared none.

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